

NOTES

Preparation and Characterisation of Mixed (Calcium+Barium+Zinc) Hydroxylapatites

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HYDROXYLAPATITE is assigned the formula $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2(\text{CaHA})$. Hydroxylapatite, now is recognised as the most important of the inorganic compounds in the structure of bones and teeth¹. Apatite undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions². $\text{Ca}^{II} \rightarrow \text{Ba}^{II}$ and/or Zn^{II} ion replacement reactions in CaHA is of extreme biological significance. They form the basis of incorporation of Ba^{II} and Zn^{II} ion into human skeletal system according to the following equation:

where, $n = 1$.

Solid solutions of calcium, barium and zinc hydroxylapatite were prepared separately earlier³ by firing mixture containing various proportions of calcium, barium and zinc hydroxylapatites at about 1300°. These samples prepared by the solid state reaction were, however, found to be discontinuous and non-homogeneous.

Now an attempt has been made at a new method of preparation of the homogeneous solid solutions of

mixed (Ca+Ba+Zn) hydroxylapatites over the entire compositional range by the method of co-precipitation⁴⁻⁶.

Stoichiometric quantities of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (Solution A) and a solution containing Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} and Zn^{II} ions in the proportion desired for the solid solutions (Solution B) were prepared separately in carbon dioxide-free double-distilled water. At pH 11, Solutions A and B were taken separately in the separating funnels and added dropwise to the content of the flask simultaneously. The precipitate and mother liquor were aged by boiling under reflux for 30 min to improve the homogeneity and crystallinity of the precipitate, and the maintenance of the desired pH during precipitation was ensured by testing the filtrate after separation of the precipitate. Since any alteration of pH of the medium during precipitation leads to the formation of calcium deficient apatites⁷. The precipitate was washed thoroughly with double-distilled water to free it from ammonium salts. Samples dried at 100° for few hours were analysed colorimetrically and their molar volumes were determined by density method using toluene⁸ as a solvent.

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples were obtained with Siemens powder diffractometer with NaCl(TL) counter employing CuK_α (Ni-filtered) radiation with a scanning speed of 1 degree (2 θ) per min (using tube voltage of 30 kV and 24 mA, respectively). The d-spacing and the corresponding a and c parameter values were calculated by the well known method of Azaroff⁹ and from these unit cell volumes of the samples were calculated and given in Table 1.

The results of chemical analysis of the samples were given in Table 1. Based on the fact that a mole of each sample has a total 10 g-atoms of calcium and/or barium and/or zinc, the molecular formulae of the samples were calculated from the

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF MIXED (Ca+Ba+Zn)-HYDROXYLAPATITES AND THEIR SOLID SOLUTIONS

Sample no.	Analysis %				Mol. formula	Mol. vol.	g-atom ratio $\frac{(\text{Ca} + \text{Ba} + \text{Zn})}{\text{P}}$	Lattice parameter μm	Unit cell volume $\sqrt{3}/2 a^3 c$
	Ca	Ba	Zn	P					
1.	89.88			18.51	$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	338.22	1.665	9.37 6.86	523.12
2.	28.28	13.31	5.16	16.38	$\text{Ca}_8\text{Ba}_{1.1}\text{Zn}_{0.9}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	340.18	1.666	9.42 6.91	551.02
3.	25.32	12.83	10.76	16.54	$\text{Ca}_{7.1}\text{Ba}_{1.05}\text{Zn}_{1.95}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	336.24	1.662		
4.	20.8	13.33	14.89	15.68	$\text{Ca}_{6.15}\text{Ba}_{1.15}\text{Zn}_{2.7}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	338.14	1.664	9.35 6.84	517.86
5.	16.89	10.88	21.82	15.5	$\text{Ca}_{5.05}\text{Ba}_{1.95}\text{Zn}_{3.0}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	337.28	1.665		
6.	12.76	12.73	25.82	14.98	$\text{Ca}_{3.95}\text{Ba}_{1.15}\text{Zn}_{4.9}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	332.64	1.664	9.28 6.77	504.91
7.	9.76	10.96	31.06	14.83	$\text{Ca}_{3.05}\text{Ba}_{1.95}\text{Zn}_{5.0}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	336.96	1.662		
8.	6.65	11.76	34.63	14.47	$\text{Ca}_{2.1}\text{Ba}_{1.1}\text{Zn}_{6.8}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	338.08	1.666	9.21 6.71	492.92
9.	3.84	11.07	38.67	14.27	$\text{Ca}_{1.25}\text{Ba}_{1.05}\text{Zn}_{7.7}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	336.72	1.666		
10.		11.78	43.16	13.86	$\text{Ba}_{1.15}\text{Zn}_{8.85}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	333.68	1.665	9.11 6.62	475.80
11.			51.98	14.79	$\text{Zn}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	347.84	1.666	9.02 6.52	459.40

results of columns 2-4 and included in column 6 of the Table 1. The g-atom ratio $(Ca+Ba+Zn)/P$, in a mole of each sample was calculated from the results of columns 2-5 and given in column B of the Table. The fact that the observed value of molar g-atom ratios of Ca/P , Ba/P , Zn/P for the end members and $(Ca+Ba+Zn)/P$, were found to be equal to 1.645 (theoretical 1.67) is consistent with the formation of homogeneous solid solution¹⁰. This was further supported by the closeness of the values of molar volumes of the end members and those of the intermediate samples which lie within the range of end members.

The formation of solid solutions can be further confirmed by the X-ray diffraction analysis. It is well established that all the members of the apatite series exhibit hexagonal crystals, belonging to hexagonal bipyramidal class-6/m (space group $P6_3/m$)^{11,12}. Lattice parameter showed unit cell dilation and contraction consequent upon the introduction of bigger ion Ba^{II} (1.35 Å) and smaller ion Zn^{II} (0.74 Å), respectively in place of Ca^{II} ion (0.99 Å) in the apatite lattice. Such dilation and contraction with the proportion of $Ca-Ba-Zn$ HA was evident that the unit cell volume of the sample calculated on the basis of the experimentally determined lattice constant increased with the proportion of barium content and decreased with the proportion of zinc content in $Ca-Ba-Zn$ HA.

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N_1 -Substituted-3,5-dimethylpyrazoles and N_1 -Substituted-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones and Related Compounds as Possible Fungicides

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PYRAZOLE derivatives have been associated with antifungal¹, antibacterial² and antimicrobial³ activities. Irikura⁴ reported that 3,5-dimethylpyrazoles have antidiabetic property. Substituted pyrazolones have been known as antibacterial⁵, antifungal⁶, antimicrobial⁷ and antiinflammatory⁸ agents. We have, therefore, synthesised the title compounds which might show enhanced biological activity due to the presence of an additional aryloxy-acetyl/carbonyl moiety.

N_1 -Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazoles (1) were prepared by refluxing aroyl/aryloxyacetylhydrazine with acetylacetone. N_1 -Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones (2) have been obtained by the reaction of aroyl/aryloxyacetylhydrazine and ethyl acetoacetate. The condensation of 2 with an aryl aldehyde in the presence of fused sodium acetate and glacial acetic acid yielded corresponding monoarylidene derivatives (3). 3 decolourise bromine water and show a broad peak at $\sim 1695\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the presence of ring ketone.

The compounds were characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight determination, ir and nmr spectra.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra of the compounds were recorded in $CDCl_3$ solution. The compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazines: These were prepared by the method of Conti⁹.

N_1 -Aroyl/aryloxyacetyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazoles¹⁰ (1): A methanolic solution (20 ml) of aroyl/aryloxyacetyl hydrazine (0.01 M) and acetylacetone (0.01 M) was refluxed gently for 3 h. On evaporation, the solid obtained was washed and recrystallised with aqueous ethanol: (1) $R=2,6-(CH_3)_2-C_6H_3-OCH_3$, (87%), m.p. 68° ; ν_{max} 1600 (CO.N), 1540 (C=N), 1050 (C-O-C-) and 745 cm^{-1}